

The logo features a central orange circle with a white flower-like pattern. This is surrounded by three smaller circles (one blue at the top, two green at the bottom) connected by curved lines. The entire graphic is set against a background of large, faint, overlapping circles in light blue, light green, and yellow, with a magnifying glass icon in the upper right.

ODECO

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECOsystem

D1.7

Training Week 5

“Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem”

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CBS	Copenhagen Business School
CTG	Center for Technology in Government
EC	European Commission
EU PO	European Union Publications Office
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
ECTS	European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
GFS	GoForeSight
GUT	Gdańsk University of Technology
LC	Lisbon Council
LLM	Large Language Model
M	Month
MS	Milestone
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OD	Open Data
ODECO	Open Data ECOsystem
SB	Supervisory Board
TW	Training Week
UNU	United Nations University
UoM	University of Macedonia
UWK	University of Continuing Education Krems
WP	Work Package

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
Beneficiary			
1	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherlands
2	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	France
4	Universidad de Zaragoza	UNIZAR	Spain
5	Panepistimio Aigaiou	UAEGEAN	Greece
6	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	Denmark
7	Università degli Studi di Camerino	UNICAM	Italy
8	Farosnet S.A.	FAROSNET S.A.	Greece
Partner organisations			
1	7eData	7EDATA	Spain
2	Digitaal Vlaanderen	DV	Belgium
3	City of Copenhagen	COP	Denmark
4	City of Rotterdam	RDAM	Netherlands
5	CoC Playful Minds	CoC	Denmark
6	Derilinx	DERI	Ireland
7	ESRI	ESRI	Netherlands
8	Maggioli S.p.A	MAG	Italy
9	National Centre of Geographic Information	CNIG	Spain
10	Open Knowledge Belgium	OKB	Belgium
11	SWECO	SWECO	Netherlands

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
12	The government lab	GLAB	United States of America
13	Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure	ADSI	Denmark
14	GFOSS Open Technologies Alliance	GFOSS	Greece
15	Inno3 Consulting	IC	France
16	Regione Marche	RM	Italy
17	Open Data Institute	OCI	United Kingdom
18	Swedish National Archives	SwNA	Sweden

1. Introduction

1.1. Training week program objective

The fifth Training Week (TW) of the ODECO project was organized by the University of the Aegean (UAEGEAN) in Samos, Greece. ODECO partners agreed in organizing the training week in the period August 26th-30th, 2024.

In defining the program of the week, the following relevant objectives/aspects were considered:

1. Feedback from the previous TW and needs expressed by the ESRs.
2. The description of the objectives of the TW in the DoA (Description of Action).
3. Deliverables that had to be delivered by the consortium in the upcoming period.
4. Involvement of external actors and of ODECO partners so to permit the exchange of ideas and point of views with people not involved in the ODECO project.
5. Inclusion of social events to enhance collaboration and professional bonding among the ESRs, and to reinforce the relationships among the ODECO partner members.
6. Inclusion of classes on relevant topics, as foreseen by the DoA.
7. Inclusion of training that focused on skills acquisition.
8. Inclusion of Master classes, an Ideathon, and Workshops by partner organizations and invited guests.

In the following Sections, the organizational context and the reported objectives to setup the final program of the week are described.

1.2. Setup of the program

The first input that was considered for the organisation of the TW5 agenda, was the feedback provided by the ESRs after the previous TW (TW4) held in KU Leuven, Belgium last April. More specifically, ESRs suggested that it was *"better to avoid online presentations"* and focus on *"practical and group activities"* while considering *"the possibility to interact with external experts/users"* as a *"must have"*. Therefore, the organizers, in consultation with the Supervisory Board, decided to plan a TW that focused on **networking** opportunities, **workshops**, as well as specific **training** aimed at skills acquisition.

Training week 5 in Samos was the last training week of the ODECO project, after acquiring a lot of experiences, comments, and suggestions all the way from the previous training weeks, and activities. ODECO TW5 was organised in conjunction with UAEGEAN's [11th International Summer School on Digital Government – OpenGov2024](#), this year focusing on the circular concept of Open Data for Artificial Intelligence (AI) and AI for Open Data.

ESRs were asked beforehand if they would like to arrange workshops, training, or want to get opinion on their topic(s) in this training week. A summary of the training week is:

- Experts in Open Government, Open Data, Digital governance, AI, Public administration, large language models (LLMs), and Research methodologies were invited on the premises.
 - Institutions involved: All ODECO Beneficiaries, the Publications Office of the EU, the EU Commission (EC), the Greek Digital Innovation Hub for Digital Governance (DigiGOV-innoHUB Greece), Gdańsk University of Technology (GUT), University of Continuing Education Krems (UWK), University of Macedonia (UoM), Lisbon Council (LC), Copenhagen Business School (CBS), GoForeSight (GFS) Institute Slovenia, United Nations University (UNU), Center for Technology in Government (CTG UAlbany), and Inspiring Futures.
- Research Ideas workshop: Participants explored possible future synergies for research proposal writing, collaboration on research papers, books, and MOOC development.

- Open Data IDEATHON: An event organized by UAEGEAN where participants, in teams, were asked to develop a technical solution idea to tackle challenges faced by non-government open data holders to contribute data. This Ideathon was also organised to facilitate the results of currently running ODECO Deliverable D4.2.
- Master classes:
 - Assessment Methodologies in Open Data Initiatives
 - Ethical and Sustainable Digital Participation in the Public Sector
 - Research Methodologies - Develop your Method
- Workshops: Six workshops were organized in this training week
 - A Method to Evaluate Chatbots in the Public Sector
 - Open Data Journalism
 - New Research Ideas (joint)
 - Social equity and open data
 - OPENVERSE
 - DigiGOV-innoHUB
- Social Events:
 - Welcome Reception
 - Social dinner
 - Wine tasting at a local Samian winery during Wednesday's lunch
 - Excursion to a village and magnificent beach in Samos

Table 1: General objectives of Training Week

Objectives of the DoA	Implementation in the TW
ODECO Network Day (all days)	The students had the opportunity to meet with EC Open data experts and the EDIH GR-gigiGOV-innoHUB representatives, as well as tutors and researchers in the data processing domains from various universities outside the core consortium. Social events were organised for that purpose.
ODECO Master Class IV, Inclusiveness: concepts, approaches, and public sector perspective and practices. Inclusiveness, Private sector perspectives and practices and citizens' perspectives and practices	Three master classes were designed and delivered in the first 3 days of the programme covering the following topics: Assessment Methodologies in Open Data Initiative; How to Evaluate Chatbots in the Public Sector?, as a real case of evaluation; Research Methodologies - Develop your Method.
Professional Skills Training	Various workshops were organised and delivered throughout the TW. These workshops were delivered by senior researchers showcasing the right way to get results doing your research. In addition, organisational analysis perspectives - real cases, design thinking, presentation was delivered.
Communicating and disseminating research (day 3)	ESRs lightning presentations [5 minutes each] Current research developments & Next research ideas (Feedback from the EU Publications Office Representatives).

Objectives of the DoA	Implementation in the TW
Project acquisition and funding, writing a business plan/case (day 3)	Workshop 3: New Research Ideas (joint), Session Lead: Harris Alexopoulos, UAEGEAN
Outreach Event (days 1, 2, 3, and 4)	Open Data Ideathon, OpenGov2024 summer school sessions.

1.3. Location

The training week took place at the Provatari Building, located within the UAEGEAN premises. The university buildings are spread across Karlovasi town, but Provatari was the closest to Karlovasi Port and right by the beach. Participants found the week to be highly social, thanks to the captivating environment and charm of Samos Island. Despite this, the group work was successfully completed, often at the port of Karlovasi, offering stunning views of the mountains and sea. The classroom was fully equipped to accommodate both onsite and online participants. It featured high-quality speakers, microphones at each chair, and camera tracking for the speakers. Additionally, it had two projectors and three large screens—two at the back and one for the presenter's view—ensuring an optimal experience for everyone.

Figure 1: University of the Aegean, Provatari Building, Samos

Figure 2: Photo of the Training Week corridor and welcome desk

Figure 3: Provatari building Lecture Hall, University of the Aegean

1.4. Certificates of achievement

The SB agreed to issue a Certificate of Achievement for the training week at UAEGEAN for 50 hours workload as each country has different standards for what workloads reflect ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System).

1.5. Supervisors attending the training week

Table 2: Supervisors attendance

Beneficiary	Supervisor name	Attendance
KU Leuven	Joep Crompvoets	In person, days 1-3
TU Delft	Bastiaan van Loenen	In person, days 1-4
UNICAM	Andrea Polini	In person, days 1-5
UAEGEAN	Charalampos Alexopoulos	In person, days 1-5

Beneficiary	Supervisor name	Attendance
UAEGEAN	Yannis Charalabidis	In person, days 2-3
FAROSNET	Antonis Furlis	In person, days 3-5
AAU	Birger Larsen	In person, days 1-5

1.6 Social Activities

To strengthen team building and networking between ESRs, the OpenGov2024 summer school participants, and invited speakers, 4 social activities were organised and carried out. On the first day (August 26th), in the evening, a Welcome Reception took place at the port of Karlovasi, at Luigi. There, the ODECO consortium and summer school participants enjoyed light food and local Samian wine under a clear sky, accompanied by delicious local ice-cream.

Figure 4: Welcome Reception at Luigi by the port of Karlovasi

On the second evening (August 27th), dinner at the local restaurant Dionysos took place. There, the ODECO consortium had the chance to enjoy traditional Greek food and drinks, accompanied with some live music.

Figure 5: Dinner at Dionysos restaurant

During lunch break of the 3rd day (August 28th), a visit to the local Samos wine cooperation took place. There, participants had the chance to try a variety of local wines while enjoying the light lunch prepared.

Figure 6: Wine-tasting at the Samos Wine Cooperative, Karlovasi

On the 4th day, right after the Open Data Ideathon which occupied fully August 29th, an excursion to a beach on the other side of the island was planned. The little town of Marathokampos, on the southern side of Samos was a great way to close the day, as the trip included a visit to the beach, while many restaurants in close proximity offered good options for food.

Figure 7: On the way to Marathokampos village, taken from the bus

The summer school (OpenGov2024) and ODECO TW5 participants also received a gift bag upon their arrival in Samos Island. The UAEGEAN gift bag contained a vase of local Samian wine, and

the famous Pythagoras cup, an ancient design and functional piece of handmade pottery- Samos (among others) also boasting a long history in pottery.

Figure 8: Gift bags for Participants: Bags, badges, program, Pythagoras cup, and local honey

2. Day 1 – Exploring AI and Open Governance: Foundations, Competencies, and Future Models

2.1. Objectives, activities, and program

The first day of the training week was designed to introduce participants to key concepts in open governance, AI in the public sector, and the role of digital technology in building democratic organizations. The day started with registration at the Provatari Building, followed by a morning coffee session, allowing participants to network and familiarize themselves with the environment. The official opening session began with an introduction to the OpenGov2024 initiative by Yannis Charalabidis and Harris Alexopoulos from UAEGEAN, who also provided an overview of the Open Data Hackathon. This was followed by the first lecture, led by Joep Crompvoets from KULEUVEN, which explored whether AI in the public sector is a breakthrough or just hype.

After a short coffee break, the second session delved deeper into AI and governance. Rony Medaglia from Copenhagen Business School gave a lecture on the competencies required for implementing AI in public administration, followed by Michel Avital, also from Copenhagen Business School, who discussed how digital technologies can help build democratic organizations. An e-lecture by Blaž Golob from the GFS Institute in Slovenia explored future governance models, considering AI, AGI, and ASI potential.

Following a light lunch, the afternoon session began with a master class by Dimitris Sarantis from the United Nations University on assessment methodologies in open data initiatives. Theresa A. Pardo from CTG UAlbany delivered an e-lecture focusing on the intersection of AI, data, and climate action. The day concluded with a welcome reception at Luigi, located at Karlovasi Port, providing participants with a chance to socialize and discuss the day's topics in a more informal setting.

Table 3: Program Day 1

Start	End	
		Monday, August 26th, 2024
09.00	9.30	Registration, Venue: Provatari Building
9.30	10.00	Morning Coffee
10.00	11.00	OpenGov Session 1: Introduction to OpenGov2024 + OD Hackathon basics: Yannis Charalabidis & Harris Alexopoulos, UAEGEAN
11.00	11.40	Lecture 1: AI in the Public Sector: Hit or Hype? Joep Crompvoets, KULEUVEN
11.40	12.00	Coffee Break
12.00	13.30	OpenGov Session 2: Lecture 2: Competencies for AI in the public sector, Rony Medaglia, Copenhagen Business School Lecture 3: Building Democratic Organizations with Digital Technology, Michel Avital, Copenhagen Business School e-Lecture 1: Foresight/AI/AGI and ASI potential new models of governance, Blaž Golob, GFS Institute, Slovenia
13.30	14.30	Light Lunch
14.30	15.30	OpenGov Session 3:

Start	End	
		Master Class 1: Assessment Methodologies in Open Data Initiatives, Dimitris Sarantis, United Nations University
15.30	16.00	e-Lecture 2: AI, Data and Climate Action, Theresa A. Pardo, Center for Technology in Government (CTG UAlbany)
	20:00	Welcome Reception - Luigi, Karlovasi Port

Figure 9: Welcome and Introductory presentation by Harris Alexopoulos

Figure 10: Day 1 activities, lessons, group photos, and discussion

3. Day 2 – AI, LLMs, Open Data, and Public Participation

3.1. Objectives, activities, and program

The second day of the training week focused on the application of LLMs, NLP, and AI in the public sector, along with the ethical dimensions of digital participation. The day began with registration at the Provatari Building, followed by a morning coffee session that provided participants an opportunity to connect.

The first session of the day introduced the use of advanced technologies for open data. Andrea Polini from the University of Camerino delivered a lecture on the role of LLM in open data initiatives. This was followed by a joint presentation from Nina Rizun of Gdańsk University of Technology and Mariia Rizun of the University of Economics in Katowice, who explored NLP techniques for data analysis and visualization. Sven Schade from the European Commission concluded the session with an e-lecture on the trustworthy use of AI in public governance.

After a coffee break, the second session shifted focus to evaluating AI tools in public administration. Efthimios Tambouris from the University of Macedonia delivered a lecture on evaluating chatbots in the public sector, followed by a practical workshop that introduced a method for assessing these AI-driven tools.

Following a light lunch, the third session of the day explored ethical and sustainable digital participation. Noella Edelmann from the University of Continuing Education Krems (UWK) led a master class, discussing how to foster ethical practices in digital participation initiatives within the public sector. The day wrapped up with a workshop on open data journalism, led by Georgios Papageorgiou from UAEGEAN/HuffPost, where participants explored techniques for utilizing open data in journalistic practices.

The day concluded with a formal dinner at Dionysos Restaurant, offering attendees the opportunity to reflect on the day's discussions and further network in a relaxed environment.

Table 4: Program Day 2

Start	End	
		Tuesday, August 27th, 2024
09.00	09.30	Registration, Venue: Provatari Building
9.30	10.00	Morning Coffee
10.00	11.40	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>OpenGov Session 4:</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Lecture 5: Large Language Models (LLMs) for Open Data</u>, Andrea Polini, University of Camerino</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Lecture 6: NLP for Data Analysis and Visualisation</u>, Nina Rizun, Gdańsk University of Technology, Mariia Rizun, University of Economics in Katowice</p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>e-Lecture 3: Trustworthy use of AI for Public Governance</u>, Sven Schade, European Commission</p>
11.40	12.00	Coffee Break
12.00	13.30	<p style="text-align: center;"><u>OpenGov Session 5:</u></p> <p style="text-align: center;"><u>Lecture 7: How to Evaluate Chatbots in the Public Sector?</u> Efthimios Tambouris, University of Macedonia, Greece</p>

Start	End	
		<i>Workshop 1: A Method to Evaluate Chatbots in the Public Sector</i> , Efthimios Tambouris, University of Macedonia, Greece
13.30	14.30	Light Lunch
14.30	16.30	<u>OpenGov Session 6:</u> <i>Master Class 2:</i> <i>Ethical and Sustainable Digital Participation in the Public Sector</i> , Noella Edelmann, University of Continuing Education Krems (UWK) <i>Workshop 2: Open Data Journalism</i> Georgios Papageorgiou, UAEGEAN/Huffpost
20:00		<i>OpenGov2024 Dinner – Dionysos Restaurant</i>

Figure 11: Noella Edelmann presenting "Ethical and Sustainable Digital Participation in the Public Sector" (Left) and Efthimios Tambouris presenting "How to Evaluate Chatbots in the Public Sector?" (Right)

Figure 12: Dinner at Dionysos restaurant

4. Day 3 – ESRs work: current and future perspectives, Research methodologies, and innovative session topics

4.1. Objectives, activities, and program

The third day of the training week emphasized research methodologies, the development of new research ideas, and the role of open data in promoting social equity. The day began with registration at the Provatari Building, followed by a morning coffee session.

The first session kicked off with a workshop led by Harris Alexopoulos from UAEGEAN, where participants brainstormed and shared new research ideas in an interactive, collaborative environment. This was followed by a master class from Noella Edelmann from UWK on developing effective research methodologies, providing guidance on how participants can refine their research approaches.

After a coffee break, the next session focused on the ODECO ESRs as they delivered lightning presentations, sharing updates on their current research in just five minutes each. This was followed by a roundtable discussion, where Els Breedstraet and Nataliya Rozbroj Jasinskaja from the European Commission offered feedback and insights on the ESR projects, encouraging further exploration of next research steps.

The midday break included a light lunch and a wine-tasting experience at the Samos Cooperative Winery, offering participants a cultural and social interlude.

The afternoon resumed with a workshop on social equity and open data, led by Caterina Santoro from KULEUVEN. This was followed by a lecture by Eleni Petra from the Athena Research Institute in Greece, focusing on open science and its integration with open data projects. The session concluded with a workshop on the OPENVERSE project, facilitated by Gianluca Misuraca, Pierre Rossel, and Francesco Mureddu, who provided insights into fostering innovation through open data initiatives.

The day concluded with an ODECO Supervisory Board meeting, followed by an exclusive dinner for the invited speakers, offering an opportunity to further discuss ideas and foster collaboration in a relaxed setting.

Table 5: Program Day 3

Start	End	
		Wednesday, August 28th, 2024
9.00	9.30	<i>Registration, Venue: Provatari Building</i>
9.30	10.00	Morning Coffee
10.00	10.50	<u>OpenGov Session 6:</u> <u>Workshop 3: New Research Ideas (joint)</u> , Session Lead: Harris Alexopoulos, UAEGEAN
10.50	11.40	<u>Master Class 3: Research Methodologies - Develop your Method</u> , Noella Edelmann, University of Continuing Education Krems (UWK)
11.40	12.00	Coffee break
12.00	13.30	<u>ODECO TW5 Session 1:</u> <i>ESRs lightning presentations [5 minutes each]</i> Current research developments: 3 min Next research ideas: 2 min

Start	End	
		ESR Projects Feedback - Roundtable , Els Breedstraet & Nataliya Rozbroj Jasinskaja, European Commission
13.30	14.30	Light Lunch - Wine Tasting at Samos Cooperative Winery
14.30	15.15	ODECO TW5 Session 2:
15.15	15.45	Workshop 4: Social equity and open data , Caterina Santoro, KULEUVEN
16.00	17.30	Lecture 8: Open Science and Open data projects , Eleni Petra, Athena Research Institute, Greece
		Workshop 5: OPENVERSE , Gianluca Misuraca & Pierre Rossel, Inspiring Futures & Francesco Mureddu, Lisbon Council
17.30	18.30	ODECO Supervisory Board Meeting
21.30	-	<i>Invited Speakers Dinner</i>

Figure 13: ESRs presenting their work to the audience comprised of experts from academia and industry

5. Day 4 – The Open Data IDEATHON and Ecosystem Development

5.1. Objectives, activities, and program

The fourth day of the training week was centered around the Open Data IDEATHON, which encouraged participants to collaboratively generate innovative solutions to real-world challenges using open data. The day began with registration at the Provatari Building, followed by a morning coffee session that set the stage for a day of creative problem-solving.

The first session introduced the IDEATHON, with a focus on the challenges set by DigiGOV-innoHUB and ODECO D4.2. Participants were briefed on the objectives of the event and the open data challenges they would address. This was followed by a session on organizational analysis, where G. Yiannarakis, Nina Rizun, Mariia Rizun, and Noella Edelmann led discussions on design thinking and shared real case studies to inspire participants. A Q&A session allowed for in-depth exploration of ideas.

After a coffee break, the teams for the IDEATHON were formed, with guidance from session leaders Nina Rizun, Noella Edelmann, Els Breedstraet, Nataliya Rozbroj Jasinskaja, and Mariia Rizun. Teams then began working on their solutions, applying the design thinking methodologies discussed earlier in the day. Following a light lunch, participants returned to their IDEATHON projects, continuing to refine their solutions. The day culminated in the announcement of the winning teams, showcasing the most innovative and impactful ideas developed during the event. To celebrate the successful completion of the IDEATHON, participants were invited to take a coach trip to Marathokampos Beach, offering an opportunity to relax and reflect on the day's accomplishments in a scenic setting.

An overview of the exact activities as planned in the daily program is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Program Day 4

Start	End	
		Thursday, August 29th, 2024
9.00	9.30	<i>Registration, Venue: Provatari Building</i>
9.30	10.00	Morning Coffee
10.00	11.00	<i>Open Data IDEATHON DigiGOV-innoHUB + ODECO D4.2 Challenges</i>
11.00	11.40	<i>Organisational analysis perspectives - real cases, design thinking, presentation, Q&A</i> Session Leads: G. Yiannarakis, N. Rizun, M. Rizun, N. Edelmann
11.40	12.00	Coffee break
12.00	13.30	<i>Open Data IDEATHON (creation of teams and work)</i> Session Leads: Nina Rizun, Noella Edelmann, Els Breedstraet, Nataliya Rozbroj Jasinskaja, Mariia Rizun
13.30	14.30	Light Lunch
14.30	15.30	OD IDEATHON Work
15.30	16:30	IDEATHON Outcomes - Winning Teams Announcement
16.30		<i>Coach to Marathokampos Beach</i>

Figure 14: Open Data IDEATHON, Harris Alexopoulos presenting the rules of the Ideathon

Figure 15: Teams are presenting their ideas to the Jury for the final ranking of their solutions

6. Day 5 – Open Data Ecosystem future perspectives

6.1. Objectives, activities, and program

The final day of the training week focused on strategies for sustainable collaborations and long-term outcomes in the open data ecosystem. The day began with registration at the Provatari Building, followed by a morning coffee session to kickstart the day's activities.

The first session, led by Ramya Chandrasekhar (CNRS) and Davide di Staso (TU Delft), was a workshop on sustainable collaborations within the open data ecosystem. This was followed by a presentation by Harris Alexopoulos from UAEGEAN on the report "Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem - D5.3," which provided insights into ongoing and future efforts to enhance the sustainability of open data initiatives.

After a coffee break, the focus shifted to long-term strategies with Birger Larsen from Aalborg University presenting on the "Long-term Outcomes Strategy for ODECO" and discussing exploitation paths through a questionnaire. This session was aimed at ensuring that the outcomes of the ODECO project have lasting impact and are effectively utilized.

Following a light lunch, the final session included a discussion on the deliverables of WP4, specifically the progress and future direction outlined in the report "Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem" by KULEUVEN. The day and the training week concluded with closing notes, summarizing the key takeaways and achievements from the event.

Table 7: Program Day 5

Start	End	
		Friday, August 30th, 2024
9.00	9.30	Registration, Venue: Provatari Building
9.30	10.00	Morning Coffee
10.00	11.00	<u>ODECO TW5 Session 3:</u> <i>[WP5 I] Workshop: Sustainable collaborations in the open data ecosystem,</i> Ramya Chandrasekhar (CNRS), Davide di Staso (TU Delft)
11.00	11.40	<i>[WP5 II]: Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem - D5.3,</i> Harris Alexopoulos, UAEGEAN
11.40	12.00	Coffee Break
12.00	13.30	<u>ODECO TW5 Session 4:</u> <i>[WP6] - Long-term Outcomes Strategy for ODECO, Exploitation Paths</i> <i>(questionnaire),</i> Birger Larsen, Aalborg University
13.30	14.30	Light Lunch
14.30	16.00	<u>ODECO TW5 Session 5:</u> <i>[WP4 - D4.3] Deliverables of WP4 - discussion</i> Towards a Sustainable Open Data Ecosystem (KULEUVEN)
16.00	16.15	Closing Notes

Figure 16: ODECO and OpenGov2024 Group Photo

7. Evaluation and conclusion

7.1. Considering recommendations from TW4

All the ESR's TW4 remarks were considered during the design of the TW5 programme. More specifically, according to ESRs feedback, TW5 focused on hands-on activities that engage them in collaboration and discussion, rather than passive presentations that they should attend (organisation of the ideathon and organisation of workshops).

Moreover, TW5 programme allowed for a more balanced schedule that prioritises condensed, but focused activities and leaves them enough time to refuel for the following day (kept the TW4 programme on hours and session scheduling).

In TW5, we invited members of the EU institutions, but also other global organisations related to the Digital ready policy, research topics of the JRC, EU Publications Office, as well as, AI, GenAI, LLMs and their role for the future of open data. Finally, a specific session on career development and professional skills training from an expert in the domain was scheduled.

7.2. Evaluation

This has been the last training week of the ODECO project, so no feedback was prepared specifically on what to keep, remove, or improve in the next one.

However, this time ODECO TW5 was organised in conjunction with the 11th International Summer School of Digital Government of UAEGEAN, so an evaluation form was shared with all the participants on the last day of the event (Friday, August 30th).

7.3. Participants' Evaluation

Based on the questionnaire sent after the end of the TW5, the participants (N=18) evaluated the summer school based on the following questions. All the average scores are above the threshold of 3,5/5. Table 7 presents the scores per question that were framed as follows: "Based on your experience participating in the Summer Scholl, indicate to what extent you consider the following statements to be true.". For each statement, indicate the degree to which you consider it is true on a scale of 1=not at all, 2=a little, 3= sufficiently, 4=a lot, 5=too much.

All means of the metrics were above 3.5, which implies that the overall satisfaction and organisation were rated above the average.

In total, 83,4% of the participants would or will recommend someone else to attend the Summer School.

Table 8: Participants' average scores in Training Week 5 evaluation

[Code]. [Question]	Average
Q04[SQ001]. [The goals of the Summer School are consistent with the needs of the learners]	3,8
Q04[SQ002]. [The contents of the Summer School program are consistent with its goals]	4,2
Q04[SQ003]. [The Summer School program offered a variety of learning activities (e.g. discussions, group work, field trips, etc.)]	4,3
Q04[SQ004]. [During the course practical activities were implemented.]	3,8
Q04[SQ005]. [During the course theory of the subject was emphasized.]	3,7

[Code]. [Question]	Average
Q04[SQ006]. [I communicated in various ways (e.g. formally and informally) with everyone involved in the Summer School.]	3,9
Q04[SQ007]. [A variety of student's evaluation methods was applied.]	3,6
Q04[SQ008]. [I had enough information about the Summer School, before I got there.]	3,9
Q04[SQ009]. [I had enough information about accommodation and travelling at the place where the Summer School was carried out, before I got there.]	3,8
Q04[SQ010]. [Feedback was provided to the trainees in various ways (e.g. discussions during and after the session/lesson).]	3,7
Q04[SQ011]. [A variety of teaching approaches was applied (e.g. seminars, workshops, roundtables, groups, hands-on activities, etc.).]	3,7
Q04[SQ012]. [I follow the program's daily schedule.]	4,2
Q05[SQ001]. [The administrative support.]	3,9
Q05[SQ002]. [The Summer School website.]	4
Q05[SQ003]. [The proposed places of accommodation (e.g. hotels, rooms, etc.).]	3,5
Q05[SQ004]. [The Social events in which I participated (e.g. excursions, official meals, etc.).]	4
Q05[SQ005]. [The opportunity I have been given to promote/ exchange my research interests to others.]	4,2
Q06. The Summer School meet my expectations.	3,9